

Determination of the absolute values of Gibbs energy of hydration or solvation $\Delta G^0_{\text{abs}}(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}}$ of monovalent (alkali metal and halide) ions and other thermodynamic parameters in aqueous and non-aqueous solvents using a single standard state and analysis of $\Delta G^0_{\text{abs}}(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}}$ values based on cluster-ion solvation method[†]

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Abstract : Absolute values of Gibbs energy of hydration (h) or solvation (s) of alkali metal and halide ions $\Delta G^0_{\text{abs}}(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}}$ and other thermodynamic parameters in aqueous and non-aqueous solvents (methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, isopropanol, *n*-butanol, ethylene glycol, propylene carbonate (PC), *N*-methyl formamide (NMF), acetone, tetrahydrofuran (THF), 1,4-dioxan, acetonitrile) were determined directly using modified Born equation and a single standard state [i.e. ΔG^0 and ΔH^0 (but not ΔS^0) of H₂ gas and other elements to be zero in their elementary standard states at 1 atm. pressure (1 bar) and 298 K]. The $\Delta H^0_{\text{abs}}(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}}$ and $\Delta G^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}}$ values are calculated considering ion-dipole, ion-quadrupole interactions and without considering the interaction terms. Very few data are available in non-aqueous solvents for comparison. Most of the single ion values (particularly for the anions) suffer from limitations associated with the erroneous principle of division of solvation energies $\Delta G^0_{\text{h or s}}(\text{MX})$ or $\Delta H^0_{\text{h or s}}(\text{MX})$ of electrolytes into single ion values.

$\Delta G^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{h}}$ values determined using cluster-ion solvation data have also been presented. The values have been claimed to be most accurate in recent years. However, the method involves a number of assumptions of doubtful validity and the values cannot be regarded to be equivalent to $\Delta G^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}}$ determined by other workers using different methods.

Coupling the values of $\Delta G^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}}$ and $\Delta H^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}}$ with $\Delta G^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{g}}$ and $\Delta H^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{g}}$ values in the gaseous state, $\Delta G^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{water or org. solvent}}$, $\Delta H^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{water or org. solvent}}$ and $\Delta S^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)_{\text{water or org. solvent}}$ [values in water and in organic solvents] are determined.

Keywords : Alkali metal ions, aqueous solvent, absolute values : enthalpy and Gibbs energy of hydration or solvation of ions, Born equation or modified Born equation, cluster-ion solvation, electron affinity (EA), halide ions, ionic additivity, ion-dipole interactions, ion-quadrupole interactions, ionization potential (IP), non-aqueous solvent.

Introduction

An electrolyte when placed in different solvent systems (aqueous, non-aqueous and aquo-organic mixtures) changes the thermodynamic, kinetic, spectroscopic and transport properties etc. considerably¹⁻¹⁰. The changes arise besides factors like changes in acidic or basic prop-

erties, macroscopic dielectric constants, molar refractive indices etc. of the solvents from the variations of the structural characteristics of the solvent systems and due to ion induced perturbations resulting from the specific interactions and orientations of the solvents around the ions.

[†]Dedicated to Professor Suresh C. Ameta on his 60th birthday.

Though the changes are reflected in different thermodynamic and kinetic properties of electrolytes in different solvents but they represent the overall changes due to the electrolytes but nothing specific can be said regarding the contributions of individual ions.

However, single ion thermodynamic values (mainly the Gibbs energy changes of electrolytes) are important in understanding the different aspects of solution chemistry like ion-solvent interactions, chemical kinetics, calculation of pH, activities of ions and redox potentials (M/M^+ , $1/2X_2/X^-$) in different solvent systems on a solvent-independent scale.

The experimental determination of single ion energy values is not possible as the difference in electric potential between two media cannot be measured. Single ion Gibbs energy values are important in understanding the different aspects of solution chemistry like ion-solvent interactions, chemical kinetics, calculation of redox potentials and the validation of different theoretical models^{5,8}.

The different aspects and the importance of Gibbs energy of single ions and their determination were discussed by Born¹¹, Latimer *et al.*¹², Izmaylov¹³, Grundwald *et al.*¹⁴, Strehlow¹⁵, Feakins¹⁶, Alexander and Parker¹⁷, Bates¹⁸, Popovych¹⁹, de Ligny²⁰, Padova²¹, Friedman and Krishnan²², Criss and Salomon²³, Kim²⁴, Abraham²⁵, Blandamer²⁶, Wells and co-workers²⁷, Marcus²⁸, Kundu and co-workers²⁹, Kalidas and co-workers³⁰, Lahiri and Aditya; Lahiri and co-workers³¹, Tissandier *et al.*³², Fawcett³³, Kelly *et al.*³⁴.

Single ion Gibbs energy values cannot be determined experimentally and are obtained using different extrathermodynamic assumptions with limitations. Similarly, enthalpy or Gibbs energy of solvation of MX cannot be determined experimentally though the values are obtainable from the relation

$$\Delta X_{\text{soln}}^0(\text{MX}) = \Delta X_{\text{lattice energy}}^0(\text{MX}) + X_{\text{soln}}^0(\text{MX})$$

[X = H or G] (1)

Lattice energy can be calculated using Born-Haber cycle⁵ and $\Delta X_{\text{soln}}^0(\text{MX})$ can be determined experimentally with sufficient accuracy.

In general, conventional single ion values (mainly for monatomic ions) were determined based on the assumption that E^0 for hydrogen electrode (necessarily ΔG^0 or ΔH^0) is zero in all solvents and at all temperatures. But the single ion values (Gibbs energy or enthalpy) are con-

verted into absolute values once the absolute value of Gibbs energy or enthalpy of hydrogen ion in the desired solvent is determined using the relations (2) and (3) (for monovalent ions)

$$\Delta X_{\text{conv}}^0(\text{M}^+)_{\text{h or s}} = \Delta X^0(\text{M}^+)_{\text{h or s}} - \Delta X^0(\text{H}^+)_{\text{h or s}} \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta X_{\text{conv}}^0(\text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}} = \Delta X^0(\text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}} + \Delta X^0(\text{H}^+)_{\text{h or s}} \quad (3)$$

The absolute values of Gibbs energy and enthalpy of single ion can thus be obtained if absolute values of Gibbs energy and enthalpy of H^+ ion i.e. $\Delta G^0(\text{H}^+)_{\text{h or s}}$ and $\Delta H^0(\text{H}^+)_{\text{h or s}}$ are known.

The eqs. (2) and (3) and ionic additivity principle lead to eqs. (4) and (5)

$$\Delta X^0(\text{MX})_{\text{h or s}} = \Delta X_{\text{conv}}^0(\text{M}^+)_{\text{h or s}} + \Delta X_{\text{conv}}^0(\text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}} \quad (4)$$

$$= \Delta X^0(\text{M}^+)_{\text{h or s}} + \Delta X^0(\text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}} \quad (5)$$

The relation also holds good for clustered ion-solvation data i.e.

$$\Delta X_{\text{h or s}}^{*\text{conv}}[(\text{S})_n\text{M}^+] + \Delta X_{\text{h or s}}^{*\text{conv}}[(\text{S})_n\text{X}^-] = \Delta X_{\text{h or s}}^*[(\text{S})_n\text{M}^+] + \Delta X_{\text{h or s}}^*[(\text{S})_n\text{X}^-] \quad (6)$$

where n is the maximum number of solvent molecules associated with an ion^{32,34}.

Single ion Gibbs energy values are found to be different by different workers and are available in the literature and references cited before. Kalidas *et al.*³⁰ and Marcus²⁸ also compiled Gibbs energies of transfer of ions (mostly monovalent cations and anions).

In recent years, large cluster-ion experiments gained much importance to characterize the variation of chemical and physical properties of clusters from small gas phase monomers to bulk. The cluster-ion solvation data are utilized to determine the absolute solvation Gibbs energy or enthalpy of monovalent ions in few solvents^{32,34}.

However, the methods for the determination of the thermodynamics of single ions are based on :

- (i) the use of different standard states for the calculation of the thermodynamics of single ions in different solvents,
- (ii) the use of Born or modified Born equations,
- (iii) the principle of ionic additivity for the division of $\Delta G_{\text{h or s}}^0(\text{MX})$ (Gibbs energy of hydration (h) or solvation in organic solvents (s)) into single ion values.

In a series of articles, Lahiri and co-workers³⁵⁻³⁷ outlined the defects of the methods for the determination of

single ion thermodynamic values based on the above assumptions and suggested a modified method. The method was utilized for the determination of Gibbs energy of monovalent ions in aqueous, aquo-organic and organic solvents.

However, for the better understanding of solvation phenomenon, it is desirable to determine $\Delta H_{h \text{ or } s}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)$, $\Delta G_{h \text{ or } s}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)$ and $\Delta S_{h \text{ or } s}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)$ in different solvents and the literature provides little information.

A brief analysis of the defects outlined above and a discussion on cluster-ion solvation method are presented in this article. Moreover, $\Delta H_{h \text{ or } s}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)$, $\Delta G_{h \text{ or } s}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)$ and $\Delta S_{h \text{ or } s}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)$ values of monovalent ions in different solvents like water, methanol, ethanol, *n*-propanol, iso-propanol, *n*-butanol, *t*-butanol, ethylene glycol (EG), propylene carbonate (PC), *N*-methyl formamide (NMF), acetone, tetrahydrofuran (THF), 1,4-dioxan and acetonitrile calculated using the *modified* method suggested by Lahiri³⁵ are also presented.

Outline of the defects of the methods for determining absolute thermodynamic values of monovalent ions :

(i) *Standard states :*

The determination of the absolute values of the Gibbs' energy or enthalpy of single ions requires the absolute thermodynamic values of H^+ ion of different ions and the redox potentials of ions.

The nominal value of pH in different solvents does not necessarily imply equal proton activities in different solvents because $G_{H^+}^0$ would vary with varying acid-base properties of solvents. The usual convention is to refer electrode potentials in each solvent to the arbitrary zero of standard hydrogen electrode i.e. SHE

This, however, generates quite a large number of thermodynamically unrelated pH or emf scales as there are solvents. The assumption also means $\bar{G}_{aq \text{ or } soln}^0(H^+)$ or $\bar{G}_{hydration \text{ or } solvation}^0$ is zero in all solvents, an absurdity

in itself. Thus, the comparison of the measured H^+ ion activities (or any other results) in different solvents necessarily involve uncertainties of unknown magnitude due to the use of results based on different standard states.

(ii) *Validity of the ionic additivity principle in the determination of single ion thermodynamic properties*³⁶ :

The ionic additivity principle was utilized to effect appropriation of enthalpy and Gibbs energies of solvation of electrolyte into single ion values similar to the appropriation of equivalent conductance Λ_{MX}^0 of an electrolyte MX into single ion conductance values $\lambda_{M^+}^0 + \lambda_{X^-}^0$ at infinite dilution i.e.

$$\Lambda_{MX}^0 = \lambda_{M^+}^0 + \lambda_{X^-}^0 \text{ (Kohlrausch's law of independent migration of ions)}$$

In conductance experiments of electrolytes, equal number of positive and negative ions are discharged at the electrodes under the influence of potential gradient irrespective of the mobilities of the cations and anions. But the additivity principle is not valid for the viscosity, the thermodynamic properties etc.

The ions M^+_g and X^-_g approach each other to form MX (*g* or *s* as the case may be) [$M^+_g + X^-_g \rightarrow MX(\text{gas})$ or $MX(\text{solid})$] and this is associated with the liberation of energy known as enthalpy (ΔH_f^0) or Gibbs energy (ΔG_f^0) of formation. i.e.

$$\Delta H^0(MX)_g \rightleftharpoons \Delta H^0(M^+_g) + \Delta H^0(X^-_g) + \Delta H_f^0(MX)_g \quad (7)$$

and

$$\Delta H^0(MX)_s \rightleftharpoons \Delta H^0(M^+_g) + \Delta H^0(X^-_g) + \Delta H_f^0(MX)_{\text{solid}} \quad (8)$$

$$[\Delta H^0(MX)_s = \text{lattice energy}]$$

This is apparent from the dissociation energies of electrolytes (kJ mol^{-1}) for the gaseous and solid MX given below.

$\Delta H_f^0(MX)_g$ and $\Delta H_f^0(MX)_s$ are the heats of formation

Electrolyte	$\Delta H^0(MX)_g$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta H_f^0(MX)_g$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta H^0(MX)_s$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta H_f^0(MX)_s$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta H^0(X^-)_g$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
NaF	644	337	916	609	-265.7 (F ⁻)
NaCl	556	227	778	449	-243.4 (Cl ⁻)
NaBr	536	206	741	411	-242.2 (Br ⁻)
NaI	506	159	690	473	-225.0 (I ⁻)

$$\Delta H^0(M^+_g)_{Na^+} = 572.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$$

for the solid $(MX)_s$ and gaseous $(MX)_g$.

The enthalpy of solvation of MX, $\Delta H^0(MX)_{solv}$ and enthalpy or heat of formation of MX in solution $\Delta H^0_f(MX)_{soln}$ are

$$\Delta H^0(MX)_{solv} = \Delta H^0_{\text{lattice energy}}(MX)_s + \Delta H^0(MX)_{soln} \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta H^0_f(MX)_{soln} = \Delta H^0_f(MX)_s + \Delta H^0_f(MX)_{soln} \quad (10)$$

$\Delta H^0_f(MX)_{soln}$ and similarly $\Delta G^0_f(MX)_{soln}$ cannot be appropriated into single ion values.

Naturally,

$$\Delta H^0(MX)_{solv} = \Delta H^0(M^+)_{solv} + \Delta H^0(X^-)_{solv} + \Delta H^0_f(MX)_{soln} \quad (11)$$

as in the solid or in the gaseous state (where the ions are expected to be far apart) and is not

$$\Delta H^0(MX)_{solv} = \Delta H^0(M^+)_{solv} + \Delta H^0(X^-)_{solv}$$

It is known that $[\Delta G^0(M^+)_{h \text{ or } s} + \Delta G^0(X^-)_{h \text{ or } s}]$ calculated using Born or other equations is not equal to $\Delta G^0(MX)_{h \text{ or } s}$ i.e. either the principle of ionic additivity is not valid or Born or other equations fail. $\Delta G^0(X^-)_{h \text{ or } s}$ is usually obtained from the relation

$$\Delta G^0(X^-)_h = \Delta G^0(MX)_{solv} - \Delta G^0(M^+)_h \quad (12)$$

i.e. $\Delta G^0(X^-)_h$ has been shown to be always negative.

But $\Delta G^0(X^-)_{solv}$ if calculated using equation

$$\Delta G^0(X^-)_{solv} = \Delta G^0(MX)_{solv} - \Delta G^0_f(MX)_{soln} - \Delta G^0(M^+)_{solv} \quad (13)$$

would be a positive quantity as observed by Lahiri^{35,36} and Matsuda⁴⁰.

Thus, the $\Delta G^0(i)_h$ of ions determined using Born equation and ionic additivity cannot be regarded to be correct. However, in case of Gibbs energy of transfer from water to other solvents, $\Delta G^0_{w \rightarrow s}(MX)_{solv}$ cancellation of $\Delta G^0_f(MX)_{solid}$ (the main contributing factor for $\Delta G^0(MX)_{solv}$) makes ionic additivity principle valid within limits of experimental errors.

(iii) *Born equation, its defects :*

Born equation¹ marks the beginning of the theoretical calculation of the hydration (or solvation) energies of ions $\Delta G^0_{h \text{ or } s}(i)$ which are essentially the differences in Gibbs energy changes of ions in aqueous (or other solvent) medium $[\Delta G^0_{aq \text{ or } solv}(i)]$ of relative permittivity (ϵ) and in vacuum of relative permittivity ϵ_0 ($\epsilon_0 = 1$) ($\Delta G^0_g(i)$).

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G^0_{h \text{ or } s}(i) &= \Delta G^0_{aq \text{ or } solv}(i) - \Delta G^0_g(i) \\ &= 1/4\pi\epsilon_0.NZ^2e^2/2r_i (1/\epsilon - 1) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where $N =$ Avogadro number $= 6.023 \times 10^{23} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $Z =$ charge of an ion, $e =$ electronic charge $= 1.602 \times 10^{-19} \text{ C}$, $\epsilon_0 = 8.854 \times 10^{-12} \text{ C}^2 \text{ N}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ and $r_i =$ radius of the ion (i) in nm.

The hydration energies obtained from eq. (14) are in qualitative but not in quantitative agreement with the known values of hydration energies of cations and anions. The important criticisms made against Born equation are :

- (i) The radius of r_i (of an ion), reported to be different by different workers⁴¹⁻⁴³ should change with solvent systems⁴⁴⁻⁴⁸.
- (ii) ϵ (relative permittivity) of the solvent should vary with distance from the ion resulting from the polarization of solvent by ions and no satisfactory equation for the variation of ϵ with distance is known in spite of plausible attempts^{25b,49-55}.
- (iii) Neglect of non-electrical component ΔG^0_{neut} in the calculation of hydration energy^{20,25b,56,57}.

However, other important limitation in the use of Born equation were either neglected or ignored. These are presented as what follows :

Formation of +ve or -ve ion (in case of monovalent ions) does not mean increase or decrease in positive charge by one unit as assumed by Ghosh and Biswas⁵⁸. The assumption of increasing nuclear charge by one unit or placing a +ve charge to the outermost orbit is an absurdity. Actually the formation of monovalent cation is not the bringing a positive ion from infinity to a distance r_i though the formation of a negative ion is the bringing of a negative charge from infinity to a distance r_i . Both the charging processes i.e. removal or addition of an electron are endothermic according to Born equation but in reality they are endothermic and exothermic for cations and anions respectively, and are equal to ionization potential (IP, +ve) and electron affinity (EA, -ve).

Theory and results

Modification of Born equation³⁵⁻³⁷ :

The charging process or ionization is actually subtraction or addition of electron (charge $-e$) from or to an uncharged gaseous atom of radius r_g (hypothetical infinite distance which in reality is the distance where the effective nuclear charge is zero) against an effective nuclear charge ($+Z_A e$) of an atom in question. The ionization process involves a change in radius from r_g to r_i .

The question of changing the radii of ions or change

in the macroscopic dielectric constant of the solvent near the ions (due to polarization) does not arise for ions in the gaseous state. The charging of atoms into ions in the gaseous state should in no way be vitiated by different interactions which occur in solutions. Born equation can thus be modified and equated with the experimental values like ionization potential (IP for cations) or electron affinity (EA for anions)

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G_g^0(i)(\text{Born}) &= 1/4\pi\epsilon_0 \cdot 1/\epsilon NZ_A e^2/2 (1/r_i - 1/r_g) \\ &= \text{IP or EA} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where Z_A = effective nuclear charge = $Z - \alpha$ (Z_A is calculated in the way given by Slater⁵⁹)

Z = nuclear charge, α = screening constant.

i.e. charging an atom into an ion involves the experimental quantities like IP or EA and is independent of r_i of ion but dependent on $(1/r_i - 1/r_g)$, a constant quantity independent of medium. r_g value is dependent on r_i and vice versa. Moreover, the eq. (15) suggest $r_g > r_i$ for cations and $r_i > r_g$ for anions which are experimentally true. r_g of M^+ or X^- are calculated using Pauling and Shanon-Prewitt's radii.

Determination of $\Delta H_{\text{abs}}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)_{\text{h or s}}$, $\Delta G_{\text{abs}}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)_{\text{h or s}}$ and $\Delta S_{\text{abs}}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)_{\text{h or s}}$:

The following cycle (Fig. 1) is considered for calculation :

Fig. 1

Gibbs energy and enthalpy of hydration or solvation of M^+ or X^- ion [$\Delta G_{\text{h or s}}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)$ and $\Delta H_{\text{h or s}}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)$] or $\Delta X^0(\text{VI})$ can be written as :

$$\Delta X^0(\text{VI}) = \Delta X^0(\text{III}) + \Delta X^0(\text{IV}) + \Delta X^0(\text{V}) \quad (16)$$

(i) Gibbs energy changes due to deionization of M^+ or X^- ion (step III) :

$$\Delta G^0(\text{III}) = \Delta G_g^0(i)_{\text{deionisation}} = -\text{IP or } -\text{EA} \quad (17)$$

IP and EA are the most authentic and reliable values for

charging an atom into ion (i.e. M^+ or X^-) and are independent of the radii of gaseous ion according to eqs. (14) or (15). They are also the determining values for the calculation of hydration or solvation energies of ions.

The enthalpy value is usually calculated using the relation

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta H^0(\text{III}) &= \Delta H_g^0(i) = \Delta G^0(i) + T \Delta S^0(i) \\ &= 1/4\pi\epsilon_0 \cdot 1/\epsilon [NZ_A e^2/2] [1/r_i - 1/r_g] \\ &\quad [1 + T (\delta \ln \epsilon/dT)] \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

However, $\delta \ln \epsilon/dT$ for the gaseous state is zero i.e. $\Delta G^0(i) = \Delta H^0(i)$ in the gaseous state which is not true. Thus, the relation (12)^{60,61}

$$\Delta H_g^0(i)_{\text{deionisation}} = -(\text{IP} + 6.2) \text{ or } -(\text{EA} - 6.2) \quad (19)$$

is used to obtain $\Delta H_g^0(i)_{\text{deionisation}}$.

(ii) Energy changes due to hydration or solvation of gaseous M or X atoms (step IV) :

Gibbs energy changes of M or X atoms due to solvation of gaseous M or X atoms in different solvents are calculated in the usual way using scaled particle theory. The equation is :

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta G^0(\text{IV}) &= \Delta G^0(M \text{ or } X)_{\text{solvation}} \\ &= \Delta G_c^0 + RT \ln (RT/V_1) \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

(in terms of hypothetical unit mole fraction, V_1 is the molar volume of the solvent though molar concentration may be used for convenience). Gibbs energy changes for the creation of cavity ΔG_c^0 was calculated in the way described before^{35-37,62,63}.

$$\Delta G_c^0 = K_0 + K_1\sigma_{12} + K_2\sigma_{12}^2 + K_3\sigma_{12}^3 \quad (21)$$

r_g values of the atoms were calculated using radii values of ions of Pauling⁴¹ and Shanon-Prewitt⁴³.

Enthalpy changes due to solvation of neutral M or X atom in different solvents i.e. $\Delta H_{\text{solvation}}^0$ or $\Delta H^0(\text{IV})$ for solvation of monovalent atoms are calculated using scaled particle theory⁶²⁻⁶⁴.

$$\Delta H^0(\text{IV}) = B_0 + B_1\sigma_{12} + B_2\sigma_{12}^2 + B_3\sigma_{12}^3 \quad (22)$$

where, $B_0 = \alpha_p RT^2 y / (1 - y)$ (23)

$$B_1 = 3\alpha_p RT^2 [y / (1 - y)] / \sigma_1 \quad (24)$$

$$B_2 = 3\alpha_p RT^2 y [(1 + 2y) / (1 - y)^3] / \sigma_1^2 \quad (25)$$

$$B_3 = \pi PN / 6 \quad (26)$$

P = Pressure and N = Avogadro number.

σ_1 and σ_2 are hard sphere diameters of the solvent and solute respectively. σ_1 is calculated in the way suggested by Kim²⁴.

$$V_s = M_s/\rho_s, \sigma_s = 2r_s = (6V_s/N\pi)^{1/3} \quad (27)$$

$$\sigma_1(\text{SPT}) = (0.9275 \pm 0.0126) \sigma_s - (0.8465 \pm 0.0084) \quad (28)$$

σ_2 are taken from Pauling's radii values or Shanon-Prewitt's values.

$$\sigma_{12} = (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)/2 \quad (29)$$

y , the reduced density, is calculated using the relation

$$y = (N\pi\sigma_1^3)/6 \quad (30)$$

P , the pressure of the system, is given by

$$P/\rho kT = (1 + y + y^2)/(1 - y)^3 \quad (31)$$

where, $\rho = N/V$, where ρ is the number average density and V is the molar volume of the solvent.

$\alpha_p = (1/V)(\delta v/\delta T)_p$ is the thermal expansivity.

α_p values for the solvents are taken from the literature⁶⁵.

ΔH^0 values can also be calculated using the relation suggested by Wilhelm and Battino⁶⁴.

$$\Delta H^0(\text{IV}) = [RT^2 \alpha_p y/(1 - y)] \{ [6/(1 - y)] [2(\sigma_{12}/\sigma_1)^2 - (\sigma_{12}/\sigma_1)] + [36y/(1 - y)^2] [(\sigma_{12}/\sigma_1)^2 - (\sigma_{12}/\sigma_1) + 1/4] + 1 \} \quad (32)$$

ΔH^0 values using eqs. (22) and (32) differ slightly and the average value using eqs. (22) and (32) are taken for calculation.

The terms have usual meaning as before.

(iii) $\Delta G^0(V)$ i.e. Gibbs energy changes due to charging of monovalent atoms into ions in a solvent of relative permittivity ϵ . The values are

$$\Delta G^0(V) = IP/\epsilon \text{ or } EA/\epsilon \quad (33a)$$

and similarly

$$\Delta H^0(V) = (IP + 6.2)/\epsilon \text{ or } (EA - 6.2)/\epsilon \quad (33b)$$

using the eqs. (14) or (15), the radii values of ions may change due to solvation as utilized by Latimer *et al.*¹². A correction can easily be made using multiplication of the values obtained from eq., (15) by $r'_i/(r'_i + \Delta)$ where r'_i is the appropriate radius $|r_g - r_i|$ and Δ may be radius of the solvent or any appropriate value.

$\Delta G^0(V)$ or $\Delta H^0(V)$ i.e. ΔG^0_h or s (M^+ or X^-) and ΔG^0_h or s (M^+ or X^-) is the summation of the energy values for (i), (ii) and (iii). Gibbs energy and enthalpy of solvation of M^+ or X^- calculated in the way described before involves no ion-solvent interactions.

However, the ion-solvent interaction is an universal phenomenon but the question of ion-solvent interaction

arises only after the solvated neutral atom is charged or an ion is introduced into the solvent. The concept of cavity or hole formation is not tenable. It is not possible to introduce an ion in any solvent. The ions formed due to the dissociation of an electrolyte in solvents are accommodated in the vacant spaces of the solvent. Naturally, disruption of solvent structure and orientation of the solvent molecules around the ions and among the solvent molecules (primary solvation and secondary solvation) will take place only when the ions are introduced in a solvent. According to Buckingham⁶⁶, Bockris and Reddy⁶⁷ ion-dipole energy is equal for positive and negative ions of equal charge and radii as the direction of the dipole (solvent molecule) is inverted upon changing the sign of the ion but the model ignored the change of sign of the charged ions. Ion (cation or anion) is oriented at an angle θ with the center of the dipole at a distance r as given in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2

The ion-dipole interaction of $\Delta H^0_{I-D} \approx \Delta G^0_{I-D}$ and ion-quadrupole interactions $\Delta H^0_{I-Q} \approx \Delta G^0_{I-Q}$ should be

$$\Delta H^0_{I-D} = \pm Z_i e \Psi_r \quad (34a)$$

and

$$\Delta H^0_{I-Q} = \pm Z_i e \Psi'_r \quad (34b)$$

where $+Z_i$ and $-Z_i$ represent positive and negative ions.

μ and p_w are the dipole moment and quadrupole moment of the bulk solvent. Ψ_r and Ψ'_r represent the potentials due to the dipole and quadrupole moments at the site of the ion.

$$\Psi_r = q(1/r_1 - 1/r_2) = -\mu \cos \theta / r \approx -\mu / r \quad (35)$$

(for cations and anions as θ is very small and $\cos \theta \approx 1$)

and

$$\Psi'_r = -\mu / r + p_w / 2r^3 \quad (36)$$

Thus,

$$\Delta H_{I-D}^0 = \mp Ze\mu/r^2 \quad (37)$$

and

$$\Delta H_{I-Q}^0 = \mp Ze\mu/r^2 \pm Z_i e p_w / 2r^3 \quad (38)$$

for cations (-) and anions (+) respectively.

r in the equations correspond to $r_i + r_s$ (r_s = radius of the solvent molecule). The calculation pertains the involvement of an ion with one solvent molecule, since n (co-ordination number) number of solvent molecules are involved in the primary solvent sheath, therefore, according to Bockris and Reddy⁶⁷, the eqs. (37) and (38) should be multiplied by n . However, the process is really the replacement of the central solvent molecule by an ion and orientation of solvent molecules around the ion. The charge of the ion should be equally distributed among n -co-ordinating solvent molecules i.e. net charge on each solvent molecule is $Z_i e/n$ and the net energy due to $i-d$ or $i-q$ should be represented by eqs. (37) and (38) and not to be multiplied by n .

The expression for the ion-induced dipole interactions

$$\Delta H_{i-i-d}^0 \approx \Delta G_{i-i-d}^0 = -\alpha Z^2 N / 2(r_i + r_s)^4 \quad (39)$$

remains unchanged. α represents the polarizability of the bulk solvent. ϵ , μ and α values of different solvents are taken from literature^{65,68}.

The bulk quadrupole moments of the solvents are taken from our works based on modified Buckingham's method³⁶. The energy values due to interactions are calculated using appropriate radii values of ions.

Apparently, there may be some uncertainty in the single ion energy values using interaction terms.

Some physico-chemical data of the solvents and ions are given in Tables 1 and 2.

The absolute values for the Gibbs energy and enthalpy of hydration or solvation of monovalent ions in different solvents without or with interaction terms are recorded in Tables 3-11.

The entropy values of hydration or solvation of monovalent ions calculated from the relation

$$\Delta S_{h \text{ or } s}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-) = \{[\Delta H_{h \text{ or } s}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-) - \Delta G_{h \text{ or } s}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)]\}/T \quad (40)$$

are also recorded in Tables 3-11 (values without parenthesis).

Gibbs energy, enthalpy and entropy values of monovalent ions in aqueous or in organic solvents $\Delta G_{\text{aq or org. solv}}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)$, $\Delta H_{\text{aq or org. solv}}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)$ and $\Delta S_{\text{aq or org. solv}}^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)$ (Tables 3-11) (values in parenthesis) are calculated from the relation

Table 1

Solvents	Dielectric constant	Dipole moment (D) (esu)	Polarisability (α) $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}/10^{24}$	Quadrupole moment (P_w) (esu)	r (SPT) ($\text{\AA}$)	Thermal expansivity $\times 10^5$ (K^{-1})
Water	78.30	1.85	1.47	4.41	1.36	25.70
Methanol	32.70	1.70	3.27	4.47	1.92	118.20
Ethanol	24.55	1.69	5.13	3.65	2.22	110.30
<i>n</i> -Propanol	20.33	1.68	6.97	2.07	2.45	100.00
<i>iso</i> -Propanol	19.41	1.66	6.99	1.53	2.48	107.30
<i>n</i> -Butanol	17.51	1.66	8.80	0.19	2.65	91.80
<i>t</i> -Butanol	11.62	1.66	8.88	0.04	2.69	140.80
Ethylene glycol	40.70	2.28	5.74	6.01	2.18	61.80
PC	64.40	4.98	8.58	20.16	2.58	95.8
NMF	182.40	3.83	6.07	15.01	2.23	86.8
Acetone	20.70	2.88	6.42	9.21	2.44	142.30
THF	7.58	1.75	0.75	-13.42	2.54	114.20
1,4-Dioxan	2.209	0.45	8.63	-38.96	2.58	109.70
Acetonitrile	35.95	3.92	4.42	14.11	2.13	138.80

$D = 3.34 \times 10^{-30} \text{ cm}$, $P_w = 1.87 \times 10^{-39} \text{ Cm}^2$, $\alpha = \text{m}^3/10^{30}$,

$\text{\AA} = 10^{-8}$, $\text{cm} = 10^{-10} \text{ m}$.

Table 2

Ions	r_i (Å)	r_g (Å)	$\Delta G_{i(g)}^0$ (gaseous ions) (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta H_{i(g)}^0$ (gaseous ions) (kJ mol ⁻¹)
Li ⁺	(i) 0.60	(i) 0.92	647.0	687.5
	(ii) 0.73	(ii) 1.26		
Na ⁺	(i) 0.95	(ii) 1.37	572.8	610.0
	(ii) 1.12	(ii) 1.76		
K ⁺	(i) 1.33	(i) 2.08	479.4	515.1
	(ii) 1.51	(ii) 2.56		
Rb ⁺	(i) 1.48	(i) 2.38	456.2	491.2
	(ii) 1.66	(ii) 2.95		
Cs ⁺	(i) 1.69	(i) 2.94	425.3	459.9
	(ii) 1.81	(ii) 3.33		
F ⁻	(i) 1.36	(i) 1.19	-265.7	-255.1
	(ii) 1.19	(ii) 1.06		
Cl ⁻	(i) 1.81	(i) 1.56	-243.4	-234.0
	(ii) 1.67	(ii) 1.45		
Br ⁻	(i) 1.95	(i) 1.75	-242.2	-218.8
	(ii) 1.82	(ii) 1.64		
I ⁻	(i) 2.16	(i) 1.92	-225.0	-194.5
	(ii) 2.06	(ii) 1.82		

(i) Pauling's radii; (ii) Shanon and Prewitt's radii.

Table 3. Water

Ions	$\Delta H_{w.l.}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G_{w.l.}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta H_{w.l.}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G_{w.l.}^0$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS^0 (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -655.48 (32.02)	(i) -639.82 (7.18)	(i) -518.25 (169.25)	(i) -502.59 (144.41)	(i) -0.05 (0.08)
	(ii) -635.09 (52.41)	(ii) -618.39 (28.61)	(ii) -517.85 (169.65)	(ii) -501.15 (145.85)	(ii) -0.06 (0.08)
Na ⁺	(i) -586.34 (23.66)	(i) -569.29 (3.51)	(i) -493.74 (116.26)	(i) -476.69 (96.11)	(i) -0.06 (0.07)
	(ii) -571.78 (38.22)	(ii) -553.09 (19.71)	(ii) -492.98 (117.02)	(ii) -474.29 (98.51)	(ii) -0.06 (0.06)
K ⁺	(i) -482.29 (32.81)	(i) -461.81 (17.59)	(i) -416.42 (98.68)	(i) -395.95 (83.45)	(i) -0.07 (0.05)
	(ii) -472.30 (42.8)	(ii) -448.83 (30.57)	(ii) -414.99 (100.11)	(ii) -391.53 (87.87)	(ii) -0.08 (0.04)
Rb ⁺	(i) -458.47 (32.73)	(i) -436.20 (20.0)	(i) -399.87 (91.33)	(i) -377.60 (78.6)	(i) -0.08 (0.04)
	(ii) -449.82 (41.38)	(ii) -423.08 (33.12)	(ii) -398.37 (92.83)	(ii) -371.57 (84.63)	(ii) -0.09 (0.03)
Cs ⁺	(i) -423.05 (36.85)	(i) -394.93 (30.37)	(i) -372.66 (87.24)	(i) -344.54 (80.76)	(i) -0.09 (0.02)
	(ii) -416.45 (43.45)	(ii) -386.17 (39.13)	(ii) -369.95 (89.95)	(ii) -339.67 (85.63)	(ii) -0.10 (0.01)
F ⁻	(i) 363.48 (108.38)	(i) 367.51 (101.81)	(i) 336.59 (81.49)	(i) 340.63 (74.93)	(i) -0.01 (0.02)
	(ii) 361.98 (105.88)	(ii) 365.69 (99.99)	(ii) 336.35 (81.25)	(ii) 340.06 (74.36)	(ii) -0.01 (0.02)
Cl ⁻	(i) 378.86 (144.86)	(i) 384.45 (141.05)	(i) 352.64 (97.54)	(i) 358.23 (114.83)	(i) -0.02 (0.01)
	(ii) 379.43 (145.43)	(ii) 384.37 (140.97)	(ii) 352.64 (97.54)	(ii) 357.58 (114.18)	(ii) -0.02 (0.01)
Br ⁻	(i) 354.71 (135.91)	(i) 361.05 (118.85)	(i) 329.24 (110.44)	(i) 335.57 (93.37)	(i) -0.02 (0.06)
	(ii) 355.16 (136.36)	(ii) 361.01 (118.81)	(ii) 328.99 (110.19)	(ii) 334.84 (92.64)	(ii) -0.02 (0.06)
I ⁻	(i) 324.78 (130.28)	(i) 332.05 (107.05)	(i) 300.59 (106.09)	(i) 307.87 (82.87)	(i) -0.02 (0.08)
	(ii) 325.19 (130.69)	(ii) 331.95 (106.95)	(ii) 300.38 (105.88)	(ii) 307.13 (82.13)	(ii) -0.02 (0.08)

The values without bracket are the solvation values of M⁺ or X⁻ in water or organic solvents and within bracket are the solution values of M⁺ or X⁻ in water or organic solvents.

Table 4. Methanol

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -598.63 (88.87)	(i) -591.59 (55.41)	(i) -502.42 (185.08)	(i) -495.38 (151.62)	(i) -0.02 (0.11)
	(ii) -583.71 (103.79)	(ii) -577.74 (69.26)	(ii) -499.92 (187.58)	(ii) -493.94 (153.06)	(ii) -0.02 (0.12)
Na ⁺	(i) -543.19 (66.81)	(i) -537.41 (35.39)	(i) -475.43 (134.57)	(i) -496.61 (103.19)	(i) -0.02 (0.11)
	(ii) -530.14 (79.86)	(ii) -525.65 (47.15)	(ii) -471.72 (138.28)	(ii) -467.23 (105.57)	(ii) -0.02 (0.11)
K ⁺	(i) -443.12 (71.98)	(i) -439.69 (39.71)	(i) -393.70 (121.4)	(i) -390.27 (89.13)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -430.99 (84.11)	(ii) -429.21 (50.19)	(ii) -387.67 (127.43)	(ii) -385.89 (93.51)	(ii) -0.01 (0.11)
Rb ⁺	(i) -418.88 (72.32)	(i) -416.49 (39.71)	(i) -374.63 (116.57)	(i) -372.23 (83.97)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -405.66 (85.54)	(ii) -405.35 (50.85)	(ii) -366.56 (124.64)	(ii) -366.25 (89.95)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
Cs ⁺	(i) -378.40 (81.5)	(i) -378.05 (47.25)	(i) -340.06 (119.84)	(i) -339.71 (85.59)	(i) 0.00 (0.11)
	(ii) -369.15 (90.75)	(ii) -370.29 (55.01)	(ii) -333.74 (126.16)	(ii) -334.88 (90.42)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
F ⁻	(i) 347.53 (92.43)	(i) 342.03 (76.33)	(i) 338.44 (83.34)	(i) 332.94 (67.24)	(i) 0.02 (0.05)
	(ii) 344.10 (89.0)	(ii) 338.99 (73.29)	(ii) 337.48 (82.38)	(ii) 332.37 (66.67)	(ii) 0.02 (0.05)
Cl ⁻	(i) 369.149 (135.149)	(i) 362.31 (118.91)	(i) 357.09 (123.09)	(i) 350.26 (106.86)	(i) 0.02 (0.05)
	(ii) 367.49 (133.49)	(ii) 361.14 (117.74)	(ii) 355.98 (121.98)	(ii) 349.62 (106.22)	(ii) 0.02 (0.05)
Br ⁻	(i) 347.85 (129.05)	(i) 340.68 (98.48)	(i) 335.49 (116.69)	(i) 328.32 (86.12)	(i) 0.02 (0.10)
	(ii) 346.54 (127.74)	(ii) 339.38 (97.18)	(ii) 334.46 (115.66)	(ii) 327.29 (85.09)	(ii) 0.02 (0.10)
I ⁻	(i) 321.41 (126.91)	(i) 313.35 (88.35)	(i) 308.89 (114.39)	(i) 300.84 (75.84)	(i) 0.03 (0.13)
	(ii) 320.22 (125.72)	(ii) 312.58 (87.58)	(ii) 307.74 (113.24)	(ii) 300.10 (75.1)	(ii) 0.03 (0.13)

Table 5. NMF

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -628.35 (59.15)	(i) -619.96 (27.04)	(i) -517.68 (169.82)	(i) -509.29 (137.71)	(i) -0.03 (0.11)
	(ii) -614.65 (72.85)	(ii) -607.63 (39.37)	(ii) -514.91 (172.59)	(ii) -507.89 (139.11)	(ii) -0.02 (0.11)
Na ⁺	(i) -575.02 (34.98)	(i) -567.94 (4.86)	(i) -490.05 (119.95)	(i) -482.98 (89.82)	(i) -0.02 (0.10)
	(ii) -562.99 (47.01)	(ii) -556.55 (16.25)	(ii) -487.09 (122.91)	(ii) -480.66 (92.14)	(ii) -0.02 (0.10)
K ⁺	(i) -474.87 (40.23)	(i) -468.59 (10.81)	(i) -408.12 (106.98)	(i) -401.84 (77.56)	(i) -0.02 (0.09)
	(ii) -463.70 (51.4)	(ii) -457.88 (21.52)	(ii) -403.41 (111.69)	(ii) -397.59 (81.81)	(ii) -0.02 (0.10)
Rb ⁺	(i) -450.72 (40.48)	(i) -444.77 (11.43)	(i) -389.43 (101.77)	(i) -383.47 (72.73)	(i) -0.02 (0.09)
	(ii) -439.22 (51.98)	(ii) -433.59 (22.61)	(ii) -383.29 (107.91)	(ii) -377.67 (78.53)	(ii) -0.02 (0.09)
Cs ⁺	(i) -410.89 (49.01)	(i) -405.24 (20.06)	(i) -356.09 (103.81)	(i) -350.43 (74.87)	(i) -0.02 (0.09)
	(ii) -403.00 (56.09)	(ii) -397.35 (27.95)	(ii) -351.39 (108.51)	(ii) -345.75 (79.55)	(ii) -0.02 (0.09)
F ⁻	(i) 360.16 (105.06)	(i) 355.21 (89.51)	(i) 345.36 (90.46)	(i) 340.41 (74.71)	(i) 0.02 (0.05)
	(ii) 355.48 (100.38)	(ii) 350.81 (85.11)	(ii) 344.53 (89.43)	(ii) 339.86 (74.16)	(ii) 0.02 (0.05)
Cl ⁻	(i) 383.56 (149.56)	(i) 377.98 (134.58)	(i) 363.63 (129.63)	(i) 358.05 (114.65)	(i) 0.02 (0.05)
	(ii) 381.69 (147.69)	(ii) 376.33 (132.93)	(ii) 362.78 (128.78)	(ii) 357.43 (114.03)	(ii) 0.02 (0.05)
Br ⁻	(i) 361.65 (142.85)	(i) 355.78 (113.38)	(i) 341.05 (122.25)	(i) 335.18 (92.98)	(i) 0.02 (0.09)
	(ii) 360.12 (141.32)	(ii) 354.46 (112.26)	(ii) 340.13 (121.33)	(ii) 334.47 (92.27)	(ii) 0.02 (0.09)
I ⁻	(i) 334.31 (139.81)	(i) 328.33 (103.33)	(i) 313.21 (118.71)	(i) 307.23 (82.23)	(i) 0.02 (0.12)
	(ii) 333.25 (138.75)	(ii) 327.44 (102.44)	(ii) 312.32 (117.82)	(ii) 306.52 (81.52)	(ii) 0.02 (0.13)

$$\Delta X_{\text{aq/org. solv}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-) = \Delta X_{\text{g}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-) + \Delta X_{\text{h/s}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-) \quad (41)$$

$\Delta H_{\text{g}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)$ and $\Delta G_{\text{g}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)$ are calculated

using the eqs. (42) and (43) and the relevant values from the literature^{35,36,51}.

$$\Delta H_{\text{g}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-) = \Delta H_{\text{atomisation}}^0 + \Delta H_{\text{ionisation}}^0 \quad (42)$$

Table 6. PC

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -633.49 (54.01)	(i) -628.67 (18.33)	(i) -509.72 (177.78)	(i) -504.89 (142.11)	(i) -0.02 (0.12)
	(ii) -620.22 (67.28)	(ii) -616.43 (30.57)	(ii) -507.32 (180.18)	(ii) -503.54 (143.46)	(ii) -0.01 (0.12)
Na ⁺	(i) -580.59 (29.41)	(i) -576.61 (-3.81)	(i) -482.87 (127.13)	(i) -478.88 (93.92)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -567.72 (42.28)	(ii) -564.81 (7.99)	(ii) -479.55 (130.45)	(ii) -476.64 (96.16)	(ii) -0.01 (0.12)
K ⁺	(i) -479.22 (35.88)	(i) -477.01 (2.39)	(i) -400.89 (114.21)	(i) -398.68 (80.72)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -466.82 (48.28)	(ii) -465.83 (13.57)	(ii) -395.58 (119.52)	(ii) -394.59 (84.81)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
Rb ⁺	(i) -454.22 (36.98)	(i) -452.92 (3.28)	(i) -381.87 (109.33)	(i) -380.57 (75.63)	(i) 0.00 (0.11)
	(ii) -441.19 (50.01)	(ii) -441.09 (15.11)	(ii) -375.08 (116.12)	(ii) -374.98 (81.22)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
Cs ⁺	(i) -413.29 (46.61)	(i) -413.17 (12.13)	(i) -348.15 (111.75)	(i) -348.02 (77.28)	(i) 0.00 (0.16)
	(ii) -404.32 (55.58)	(ii) -405.06 (20.24)	(ii) -342.78 (117.12)	(ii) -343.52 (81.78)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
F ⁻	(i) 371.69 (116.59)	(i) 363.81 (98.11)	(i) 344.09 (88.99)	(i) 336.21 (70.51)	(i) 0.03 (0.06)
	(ii) 368.73 (113.63)	(ii) 361.34 (95.64)	(ii) 343.06 (87.96)	(ii) 335.67 (69.97)	(ii) 0.03 (0.06)
Cl ⁻	(i) 393.01 (159.01)	(i) 383.09 (139.69)	(i) 363.56 (129.56)	(i) 353.64 (110.24)	(i) 0.03 (0.06)
	(ii) 390.76 (156.76)	(ii) 382.28 (138.88)	(ii) 361.51 (127.51)	(ii) 353.03 (109.63)	(ii) 0.03 (0.06)
Br ⁻	(i) 369.65 (150.85)	(i) 360.39 (118.19)	(i) 340.23 (121.43)	(i) 330.96 (88.76)	(i) 0.03 (0.11)
	(ii) 368.77 (149.97)	(ii) 359.73 (117.53)	(ii) 339.31 (120.51)	(ii) 330.28 (88.08)	(ii) 0.03 (0.11)
I ⁻	(i) 342.06 (147.56)	(i) 332.33 (107.33)	(i) 312.99 (118.49)	(i) 303.26 (78.26)	(i) 0.03 (0.14)
	(ii) 341.21 (146.71)	(ii) 331.85 (106.85)	(ii) 311.94 (117.44)	(ii) 302.57 (77.57)	(ii) 0.03 (0.13)

Table 7. Ethanol

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -591.03 (96.47)	(i) -585.33 (61.67)	(i) -496.64 (190.86)	(i) -490.95 (156.05)	(i) -0.02 (0.12)
	(ii) -576.81 (110.69)	(ii) -572.31 (74.69)	(ii) -494.06 (193.44)	(ii) -489.55 (157.45)	(ii) -0.02 (0.12)
Na ⁺	(i) -537.31 (72.69)	(i) -532.92 (39.88)	(i) -469.88 (140.12)	(i) -465.48 (107.32)	(i) -0.02 (0.11)
	(ii) -524.69 (85.31)	(ii) -521.51 (51.29)	(ii) -466.34 (143.66)	(ii) -463.17 (109.63)	(ii) -0.01 (0.11)
K ⁺	(i) -438.71 (76.39)	(i) -436.54 (42.83)	(i) -389.24 (125.86)	(i) -387.07 (92.33)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -426.78 (88.32)	(ii) -426.23 (53.17)	(ii) -383.37 (131.73)	(ii) -382.82 (96.58)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
Rb ⁺	(i) -414.56 (76.64)	(i) -413.61 (42.59)	(i) -370.22 (120.98)	(i) -369.26 (86.94)	(i) 0.00 (0.11)
	(ii) -401.95 (89.25)	(ii) -402.65 (53.55)	(ii) -362.76 (128.44)	(ii) -363.46 (92.74)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
Cs ⁺	(i) -374.91 (84.99)	(i) -375.62 (49.68)	(i) -336.49 (123.41)	(i) -337.19 (88.11)	(i) 0.00 (0.12)
	(ii) -366.12 (93.78)	(ii) -368.09 (57.21)	(ii) -330.54 (129.36)	(ii) -332.51 (92.79)	(ii) 0.01 (0.12)
F ⁻	(i) 340.44 (85.34)	(i) 333.64 (67.94)	(i) 335.49 (80.39)	(i) 328.68 (62.98)	(i) 0.02 (0.06)
	(ii) 336.96 (81.86)	(ii) 330.52 (64.82)	(ii) 334.57 (79.47)	(ii) 328.13 (62.43)	(ii) 0.02 (0.06)
Cl ⁻	(i) 362.42 (128.42)	(i) 354.33 (110.93)	(i) 353.89 (119.89)	(i) 345.79 (102.39)	(i) 0.03 (0.06)
	(ii) 360.66 (126.66)	(ii) 353.03 (109.63)	(ii) 352.79 (118.79)	(ii) 345.16 (101.76)	(ii) 0.03 (0.06)
Br ⁻	(i) 341.36 (122.56)	(i) 332.82 (90.62)	(i) 332.30 (113.5)	(i) 323.76 (81.56)	(i) 0.03 (0.11)
	(ii) 340.04 (121.24)	(ii) 331.64 (89.44)	(ii) 331.46 (112.66)	(ii) 323.06 (80.86)	(ii) 0.03 (0.11)
I ⁻	(i) 315.59 (121.09)	(i) 306.36 (81.36)	(i) 306.07 (111.57)	(i) 296.83 (71.83)	(i) 0.03 (0.13)
	(ii) 314.43 (119.93)	(ii) 305.47 (80.47)	(ii) 305.08 (110.58)	(ii) 296.12 (71.12)	(ii) 0.03 (0.13)

and

$$\Delta G^0_{\text{g}}(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-) = \Delta G^0_{\text{atomisation}} + \Delta G^0_{\text{ionisation}} \quad (43)$$

$\Delta S^0_{\text{aq/org. solv}}(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)$ values are calculated in the usual way.

However, $\Delta X^0_{\text{water or org. solv}}(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)$, $\Delta X^0_{\text{h or s}}(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)$ etc. can also be calculated from the relations,

$$\Delta X^0_{\text{water or org. solv}}(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-) = \Delta X^0(\text{II}) + \Delta X^0(\text{IV}) + \Delta X^0(\text{V}) \quad (44)$$

Table 8. *n*-Propanol

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -588.37 (99.13)	(i) -583.29 (63.71)	(i) -492.19 (195.31)	(i) -487.11 (159.89)	(i) -0.02 (0.12)
	(ii) -574.97 (112.53)	(ii) -571.03 (75.97)	(ii) -489.89 (197.61)	(ii) -485.75 (161.25)	(ii) -0.01 (0.12)
Na ⁺	(i) -535.49 (74.51)	(i) -531.49 (41.31)	(i) -465.89 (144.11)	(i) -461.89 (110.91)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -522.97 (87.03)	(ii) -520.08 (52.72)	(ii) -462.52 (147.48)	(ii) -459.63 (113.17)	(ii) -0.01 (0.12)
K ⁺	(i) -437.65 (77.45)	(i) -435.66 (43.74)	(i) -386.23 (128.87)	(i) -384.24 (95.16)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -426.14 (88.96)	(ii) -425.28 (54.12)	(ii) -380.95 (134.15)	(ii) -380.09 (99.31)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
Rb ⁺	(i) -413.99 (77.21)	(i) -412.78 (43.42)	(i) -367.85 (123.35)	(i) -366.63 (89.57)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -401.70 (89.5)	(ii) -401.79 (54.41)	(ii) -360.87 (130.33)	(ii) -360.97 (95.23)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
Cs ⁺	(i) -374.75 (85.15)	(i) -374.96 (50.34)	(i) -334.71 (125.19)	(i) -334.93 (90.37)	(i) 0.00 (0.12)
	(ii) -366.41 (93.49)	(ii) -368.08 (57.22)	(ii) -329.34 (130.56)	(ii) -331.01 (94.29)	(ii) 0.01 (0.12)
F ⁻	(i) 336.87 (81.77)	(i) 329.59 (63.89)	(i) 332.55 (77.45)	(i) 325.28 (59.58)	(i) 0.02 (0.06)
	(ii) 333.69 (78.59)	(ii) 326.74 (61.04)	(ii) 331.68 (76.58)	(ii) 324.74 (59.04)	(ii) 0.02 (0.06)
Cl ⁻	(i) 358.16 (124.16)	(i) 349.88 (106.48)	(i) 350.51 (116.51)	(i) 342.22 (98.82)	(i) 0.03 (0.06)
	(ii) 356.57 (122.57)	(ii) 348.55 (105.15)	(ii) 349.63 (115.63)	(ii) 341.61 (98.21)	(ii) 0.03 (0.06)
Br ⁻	(i) 337.39 (118.59)	(i) 328.54 (86.34)	(i) 329.23 (110.43)	(i) 320.37 (78.17)	(i) 0.03 (0.11)
	(ii) 335.82 (117.02)	(ii) 327.37 (85.17)	(ii) 328.12 (109.32)	(ii) 319.68 (77.48)	(ii) 0.03 (0.11)
I ⁻	(i) 311.64 (117.14)	(i) 302.31 (77.31)	(i) 302.98 (108.48)	(i) 293.65 (68.65)	(i) 0.03 (0.12)
	(ii) 310.39 (115.89)	(ii) 301.42 (76.42)	(ii) 301.94 (107.44)	(ii) 292.96 (67.96)	(ii) 0.03 (0.13)

 Table 9. *iso*-Propanol

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -580.77 (106.73)	(i) -576.59 (70.41)	(i) -490.11 (197.39)	(i) -485.93 (161.07)	(i) -0.01 (0.12)
	(ii) -567.59 (119.91)	(ii) -564.60 (82.4)	(ii) -487.55 (199.95)	(ii) -484.56 (162.44)	(ii) -0.01 (0.13)
Na ⁺	(i) -532.10 (77.9)	(i) -529.06 (43.74)	(i) -463.81 (146.19)	(i) -460.76 (112.04)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -519.55 (90.45)	(ii) -517.87 (57.93)	(ii) -460.17 (149.83)	(ii) -458.48 (114.32)	(ii) -0.01 (0.11)
K ⁺	(i) -434.39 (80.71)	(i) -433.85 (45.55)	(i) -383.82 (131.28)	(i) -383.27 (96.13)	(i) 0.00 (0.12)
	(ii) -422.45 (92.65)	(ii) -423.61 (55.79)	(ii) -377.96 (137.14)	(ii) -379.12 (100.28)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
Rb ⁺	(i) -410.67 (80.53)	(i) -411.13 (45.07)	(i) -365.25 (125.95)	(i) -365.70 (90.5)	(i) 0.00 (0.12)
	(ii) -397.89 (93.31)	(ii) -400.26 (55.94)	(ii) -357.67 (133.53)	(ii) -360.04 (96.16)	(ii) 0.01 (0.13)
Cs ⁺	(i) -371.16 (88.74)	(i) -373.50 (51.8)	(i) -331.72 (128.18)	(i) -334.06 (91.24)	(i) 0.01 (0.12)
	(ii) -362.33 (97.57)	(ii) -366.04 (59.26)	(ii) -325.79 (134.11)	(ii) -329.49 (95.81)	(ii) 0.01 (0.13)
F ⁻	(i) 337.43 (82.33)	(i) 329.25 (63.55)	(i) 332.66 (77.56)	(i) 324.48 (58.78)	(i) 0.03 (0.06)
	(ii) 334.23 (79.13)	(ii) 326.56 (60.86)	(ii) 331.61 (76.51)	(ii) 323.94 (58.24)	(ii) 0.03 (0.06)
Cl ⁻	(i) 358.67 (124.67)	(i) 349.23 (105.83)	(i) 350.83 (116.83)	(i) 371.39 (127.99)	(i) 0.03 (0.06)
	(ii) 356.96 (122.96)	(ii) 347.96 (104.56)	(ii) 349.78 (115.78)	(ii) 340.78 (97.38)	(ii) 0.03 (0.06)
Br ⁻	(i) 337.91 (119.11)	(i) 327.90 (85.7)	(i) 329.61 (110.81)	(i) 319.59 (77.39)	(i) 0.03 (0.11)
	(ii) 336.41 (117.61)	(ii) 326.78 (84.58)	(ii) 328.53 (109.73)	(ii) 318.91 (76.71)	(ii) 0.03 (0.11)
I ⁻	(i) 312.39 (117.89)	(i) 301.69 (76.69)	(i) 303.66 (109.16)	(i) 292.95 (67.95)	(i) 0.04 (0.14)
	(ii) 311.14 (116.64)	(ii) 300.82 (75.82)	(ii) 302.58 (108.08)	(ii) 292.26 (67.26)	(ii) 0.04 (0.14)

and

$$\Delta X_{\text{h or s}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-) = \Delta X_{\text{g}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-) - \Delta X_{\text{water or org. solv.}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)$$

The results are the same.

Discussion

The thermodynamics of hydration or solvation of alkali metal ions and halide ions in water and in different organic solvents are presented in Tables 3–11.

Table 10. *n*-Butanol

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -577.48 (110.02)	(i) -573.51 (73.49)	(i) -487.96 (199.54)	(i) -483.49 (163.51)	(i) -0.02 (0.12)
	(ii) -565.52 (121.98)	(ii) -561.93 (85.07)	(ii) -485.75 (201.75)	(ii) -482.16 (164.84)	(ii) -0.01 (0.12)
Na ⁺	(i) -528.11 (81.89)	(i) -524.43 (48.37)	(i) -462.19 (147.81)	(i) -458.51 (114.29)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -516.62 (93.38)	(ii) -531.79 (41.01)	(ii) -459.13 (150.87)	(ii) -456.31 (116.49)	(ii) -0.01 (0.12)
K ⁺	(i) -432.86 (82.24)	(i) -430.69 (48.71)	(i) -383.76 (131.34)	(i) -381.58 (97.82)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -421.98 (93.12)	(ii) -420.82 (58.58)	(ii) -378.70 (136.40)	(ii) -377.54 (101.86)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
Rb ⁺	(i) -409.79 (81.41)	(i) -408.34 (47.86)	(i) -365.62 (125.58)	(i) -364.17 (92.03)	(i) -0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) -398.21 (92.99)	(ii) -397.83 (58.37)	(ii) -359.03 (132.17)	(ii) -358.65 (97.55)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
Cs ⁺	(i) -371.66 (88.24)	(i) -371.26 (54.04)	(i) -333.24 (126.66)	(i) -332.83 (92.47)	(i) 0.00 (0.11)
	(ii) -363.76 (96.14)	(ii) -364.01 (61.29)	(ii) -328.13 (131.77)	(ii) -328.38 (96.92)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
F ⁻	(i) 330.45 (75.35)	(i) 322.89 (57.19)	(i) 329.68 (74.58)	(i) 322.12 (56.42)	(i) 0.03 (0.06)
	(ii) 327.06 (71.96)	(ii) 319.82 (54.12)	(ii) 328.83 (73.73)	(ii) 321.59 (55.89)	(ii) 0.02 (0.06)
Cl ⁻	(i) 351.96 (117.96)	(i) 343.62 (100.22)	(i) 347.24 (113.24)	(i) 338.89 (95.49)	(i) 0.03 (0.07)
	(ii) 350.22 (116.22)	(ii) 342.53 (99.13)	(ii) 346.41 (112.41)	(ii) 338.71 (95.31)	(ii) 0.03 (0.06)
Br ⁻	(i) 331.47 (112.67)	(i) 322.62 (80.42)	(i) 326.04 (107.24)	(i) 317.19 (74.99)	(i) 0.03 (0.11)
	(ii) 329.93 (111.13)	(ii) 321.31 (79.11)	(ii) 325.15 (106.35)	(ii) 316.52 (74.32)	(ii) 0.03 (0.11)
I ⁻	(i) 306.14 (111.64)	(i) 296.86 (71.86)	(i) 299.97 (105.47)	(i) 290.68 (65.68)	(i) 0.03 (0.13)
	(ii) 304.82 (110.32)	(ii) 295.86 (70.86)	(ii) 298.96 (104.46)	(ii) 290.01 (65.01)	(ii) 0.03 (0.13)

Table 11. *t*-Butanol

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -552.35 (135.15)	(i) -552.59 (94.41)	(i) -468.26 (219.24)	(i) -468.49 (178.51)	(i) 0.00 (0.14)
	(ii) -539.49 (148.01)	(ii) -541.82 (105.18)	(ii) -464.85 (222.65)	(ii) -467.17 (179.83)	(ii) 0.01 (0.14)
Na ⁺	(i) -503.37 (106.37)	(i) -506.06 (66.74)	(i) -441.53 (168.47)	(i) -444.22 (128.58)	(i) 0.01 (0.13)
	(ii) -490.75 (119.25)	(ii) -496.05 (76.75)	(ii) -436.72 (173.28)	(ii) -442.02 (130.78)	(ii) 0.01 (0.14)
K ⁺	(i) -408.23 (106.87)	(i) -415.78 (63.62)	(i) -361.99 (153.11)	(i) -369.53 (109.87)	(i) 0.02 (0.15)
	(ii) -395.07 (120.03)	(ii) -406.34 (73.06)	(ii) -354.24 (160.86)	(ii) -365.51 (113.89)	(ii) 0.04 (0.16)
Rb ⁺	(i) -385.40 (105.80)	(i) -394.26 (61.94)	(i) -343.74 (147.46)	(i) -352.59 (103.61)	(i) 0.03 (0.15)
	(ii) -369.54 (121.66)	(ii) -384.15 (72.05)	(ii) -332.53 (158.67)	(ii) -347.14 (109.06)	(ii) 0.05 (0.17)
Cs ⁺	(i) -344.01 (115.89)	(i) -358.38 (66.92)	(i) -307.70 (152.20)	(i) -322.07 (103.23)	(i) 0.05 (0.16)
	(ii) -333.54 (126.36)	(ii) -351.34 (73.96)	(ii) -299.84 (160.06)	(ii) -317.64 (107.66)	(ii) 0.06 (0.18)
F ⁻	(i) 324.8 (69.70)	(i) 311.95 (46.25)	(i) 325.26 (70.16)	(i) 312.41 (46.71)	(i) 0.04 (0.08)
	(ii) 320.78 (65.68)	(ii) 308.65 (42.95)	(ii) 324.02 (68.92)	(ii) 311.89 (46.19)	(ii) 0.04 (0.08)
Cl ⁻	(i) 345.21 (111.21)	(i) 332.34 (88.94)	(i) 341.61 (107.61)	(i) 328.75 (85.35)	(i) 0.04 (0.07)
	(ii) 345.32 (111.32)	(ii) 330.76 (87.36)	(ii) 342.71 (108.71)	(ii) 328.16 (84.76)	(ii) 0.05 (0.08)
Br ⁻	(i) 326.14 (107.34)	(i) 312.11 (69.91)	(i) 321.77 (102.97)	(i) 307.75 (65.55)	(i) 0.05 (0.13)
	(ii) 326.57 (107.77)	(ii) 310.73 (68.53)	(ii) 322.92 (104.12)	(ii) 307.08 (64.88)	(ii) 0.05 (0.13)
I ⁻	(i) 305.02 (110.52)	(i) 287.28 (62.28)	(i) 299.81 (105.31)	(i) 282.07 (57.07)	(i) 0.06 (0.16)
	(ii) 303.35 (108.85)	(ii) 286.25 (61.25)	(ii) 298.49 (103.99)	(ii) 281.39 (56.39)	(ii) 0.06 (0.16)

The thermodynamic parameters of these ions in aqueous and non-aqueous solutions are also presented in Tables 3–11.

Gibbs energy of hydration or solvation of these ions in water and in organic solvents are reported in the litera-

ture and the values vary widely.

The range of values of $\Delta G_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)$ and $\Delta H_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)$ (in kJ mol⁻¹) in water and values reported by Criss and Salomen²³ and the values cited by

Marcus are given below :

Ions	$-\Delta G_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)^a$	$-\Delta H_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)^a$	$-\Delta G_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)^b$	$-\Delta H_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)^b$
Li ⁺	490.2–514.6	450.2–556.5	481.0	522.0
Na ⁺	302.9–447.7	335.6–481.2	375.0	407.0
K ⁺	229.7–351.9	251.9–376.6	304.0	324.0
Rb ⁺	212.1–330.5	222.2–338.9	281.0	299.0
Cs ⁺	195.4–298.3	192.9–305.4	258.0	274.0
F ⁻	338.9–538.5	380.7–587.0	472.0	519.0
Cl ⁻	217.6–419.7	246.9–443.5	347.0	376.0
Br ⁻	196.6–394.1	217.6–425.1	321.0	345.0
I ⁻	226.8–358.6	188.3–370.3	283.0	300.0

^aRef. 23, p. 320; ^bRef. 7, p. 107-108.

The $\Delta G_{\text{hydration}}^0$ values are widely divergent. Our values for alkali metal ions agree qualitatively (–ve) but differ quantitatively whereas for halide ions they differ both qualitatively and quantitatively. The absolute values of ions in different solvents are determined using a single standard state i.e. ΔG^0 and ΔH^0 for the elements are zero in their respective standard states.

Most of the single ion values are determined from the equal division of enthalpy and Gibbs energy of hydration or solvation [$\Delta H^0(\text{MX})_{\text{h or s}}$] and [$\Delta G^0(\text{MX})_{\text{h or s}}$] and single ion values based on Born equation considering the equality of radii of ions, and the principle of ionic addi-

tivity. KF (Bernal and Fowler⁶⁹), RbCl (Blandamer and Symons⁷⁰) and CsI (Mischenko⁷¹, Vasilev *et al.*⁷², Krestov and Klopov⁷³) are some of the electrolytes chosen for division.

However, the radii of ions like (K⁺ and F⁻), (Rb⁺ and Cl⁻) and (Cs⁺ and I⁻) reported by different workers differ considerably^{23,41-48}.

Moreover, Born equation and the principle of ionic additivity are not valid and cannot give accurate single ion values like [$\Delta H_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)$, $\Delta G_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{M}^+ \text{ or } \text{X}^-)$] for reasons given before and below.

Table 12. Ethylene glycol

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) –627.41 (60.09)	(i) –617.91 (29.09)	(i) –502.74 (184.76)	(i) –499.23 (147.77)	(i) –0.01 (0.10)
	(ii) –611.57 (75.93)	(ii) –602.17 (44.83)	(ii) –507.22 (180.28)	(ii) –497.83 (149.17)	(ii) –0.03 (0.10)
Na ⁺	(i) –568.68 (41.32)	(i) –558.81 (13.99)	(i) –483.24 (126.76)	(i) –473.36 (99.44)	(i) –0.03 (0.09)
	(ii) –555.49 (54.51)	(ii) –545.23 (27.57)	(ii) –481.29 (128.71)	(ii) –471.03 (101.77)	(ii) –0.03 (0.09)
K ⁺	(i) –467.55 (47.55)	(i) –456.86 (22.54)	(i) –404.36 (110.74)	(i) –393.67 (85.73)	(i) –0.04 (0.08)
	(ii) –456.74 (58.36)	(ii) –445.04 (34.36)	(ii) –401.09 (114.01)	(ii) –389.39 (90.01)	(ii) –0.04 (0.08)
Rb ⁺	(i) –444.66 (46.54)	(i) –432.39 (23.81)	(i) –387.85 (103.35)	(i) –375.59 (80.61)	(i) –0.04 (0.08)
	(ii) –432.93 (58.27)	(ii) –420.13 (36.07)	(ii) –382.55 (108.65)	(ii) –369.75 (86.45)	(ii) –0.04 (0.07)
Cs ⁺	(i) –405.29 (54.61)	(i) –392.45 (32.85)	(i) –355.87 (104.03)	(i) –343.03 (82.27)	(i) –0.04 (0.07)
	(ii) –398.30 (61.60)	(ii) –384.17 (41.13)	(ii) –352.45 (107.45)	(ii) –338.32 (86.98)	(ii) –0.05 (0.07)
F ⁻	(i) 347.86 (92.76)	(i) 346.06 (80.36)	(i) 336.43 (81.33)	(i) 334.19 (68.49)	(i) 0.01 (0.04)
	(ii) 344.34 (89.24)	(ii) 341.99 (76.29)	(ii) 335.98 (80.88)	(ii) 333.64 (67.94)	(ii) 0.01 (0.04)
Cl ⁻	(i) 368.00 (134.0)	(i) 365.93 (122.53)	(i) 353.64 (119.64)	(i) 351.56 (108.16)	(i) 0.01 (0.04)
	(ii) 366.78 (132.78)	(ii) 364.67 (121.27)	(ii) 353.04 (119.04)	(ii) 350.93 (107.53)	(ii) 0.01 (0.04)
Br ⁻	(i) 345.72 (126.92)	(i) 343.90 (101.7)	(i) 330.97 (112.17)	(ii) 329.16 (86.96)	(i) 0.01 (0.08)
	(ii) 344.83 (126.03)	(ii) 342.84 (100.64)	(ii) 330.43 (111.63)	(ii) 328.44 (86.24)	(ii) 0.01 (0.09)
I ⁻	(i) 318.36 (123.86)	(i) 316.74 (91.74)	(i) 303.38 (108.88)	(i) 301.76 (76.76)	(i) 0.01 (0.11)
	(ii) 317.79 (123.29)	(ii) 315.96 (90.96)	(ii) 302.88 (108.38)	(ii) 301.05 (76.05)	(ii) 0.01 (0.11)

Table 13. Acetone

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -582.33 (105.17)	(i) -582.07 (64.93)	(i) -487.77 (199.73)	(i) -487.51 (159.49)	(i) 0.00 (0.14)
	(ii) -570.66 (116.84)	(ii) -571.04 (75.96)	(ii) -485.75 (201.75)	(ii) -486.14 (160.14)	(ii) 0.00 (0.14)
Na ⁺	(i) -533.28 (76.72)	(i) -534.05 (38.75)	(i) -461.49 (148.51)	(i) -462.26 (110.54)	(i) 0.00 (0.13)
	(ii) -520.36 (89.64)	(ii) -523.72 (49.08)	(ii) -456.63 (153.37)	(ii) -459.98 (112.82)	(ii) 0.01 (0.14)
K ⁺	(i) -434.70 (80.40)	(i) -440.13 (39.27)	(i) -379.07 (136.03)	(i) -384.50 (94.90)	(i) 0.02 (0.14)
	(ii) -421.27 (93.83)	(ii) -430.26 (49.14)	(ii) -371.34 (143.76)	(ii) -380.33 (99.07)	(ii) 0.03 (0.15)
Rb ⁺	(i) -410.07 (81.13)	(i) -417.68 (38.52)	(i) -359.26 (131.94)	(i) -366.87 (89.33)	(i) 0.03 (0.14)
	(ii) -394.90 (96.30)	(ii) -407.03 (49.17)	(ii) -349.04 (142.16)	(ii) -361.17 (95.03)	(ii) 0.04 (0.16)
Cs ⁺	(i) -368.15 (91.75)	(i) -380.22 (45.08)	(i) -323.05 (136.85)	(i) -335.11 (90.19)	(i) 0.04 (0.16)
	(ii) -357.56 (102.34)	(ii) -372.82 (52.48)	(ii) -315.12 (144.78)	(ii) -330.52 (94.78)	(ii) 0.05 (0.17)
F ⁻	(i) 349.01 (93.91)	(i) 337.49 (71.79)	(i) 337.15 (82.05)	(i) 325.64 (59.94)	(i) 0.04 (0.07)
	(ii) 345.31 (90.21)	(ii) 334.58 (68.88)	(ii) 335.82 (80.72)	(ii) 325.09 (59.39)	(ii) 0.04 (0.07)
Cl ⁻	(i) 371.39 (137.39)	(i) 357.58 (114.18)	(i) 356.41 (122.41)	(i) 342.61 (99.21)	(i) 0.05 (0.08)
	(ii) 369.43 (135.43)	(ii) 356.35 (112.95)	(ii) 355.07 (121.07)	(ii) 341.99 (98.59)	(ii) 0.04 (0.08)
Br ⁻	(i) 348.67 (129.87)	(i) 336.10 (93.90)	(i) 333.31 (114.51)	(i) 320.74 (78.54)	(i) 0.04 (0.12)
	(ii) 349.26 (130.46)	(ii) 335.05 (92.85)	(ii) 334.25 (115.45)	(ii) 320.04 (77.84)	(ii) 0.05 (0.13)
I ⁻	(i) 325.75 (131.25)	(i) 309.63 (84.63)	(i) 310.12 (115.62)	(i) 294.01 (69.01)	(i) 0.05 (0.16)
	(ii) 324.27 (129.77)	(ii) 308.85 (83.85)	(ii) 308.73 (114.23)	(ii) 293.31 (68.31)	(ii) 0.05 (0.15)

Born equation :

(i) Gas-phase Gibbs energy [$\Delta G^0_g(i) = \Delta G^0(i)_{\text{atomisation}} + \Delta G^0(i)_{\text{ionization}}$] values of some monatomic ions using data of Fawcett³³ are :

Ions	$\Delta G^0_g(i)^{33}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$\Delta G^0(i)_{\text{ionization}}^{60,61}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹) (IP or EA)
Na ⁺	559.07	495.8
K ⁺	462.0	418.9
F ⁻	-273.02	-327.9
Cl ⁻	-293.39	-348.8

Whatever may be the value of $\Delta G^0_{\text{charging}}(i)$ in aqueous or organic solvents for these ions, the values must be numerically much less (eq. (14)) than the values for $\Delta G^0_g(i)$ and charging in the gas phase with the same sign. Thus, $\Delta G^0(i)_{\text{h or s}}$ should be negative for cations and positive for anions as observed by Lahiri³⁵⁻³⁷ and Matsuda⁴⁰ but contrary to the values given in the literature. The table 4 of Fawcett's paper³³ also shows that $\Delta G^0(i)_{\text{h}}$ (Gibbs energies of hydration for ions) of (K⁺ and F⁻), (Rb⁺ and Br⁻) and (Cs⁺ and I⁻) are not equal and differ considerably i.e. equal division of $\Delta G^0(MX)_{\text{hydration}}$ energies of KF, RbBr and CsI into single ion values are not tenable.

(ii) The eq. (15) shows $\Delta G^0(i)_{\text{h}}$ are negative and posi-

tive for cations and anions and are not equal for ions of equal radii as the ionization energies (equivalent to energy due to Born charging) are dependent on the effective nuclear charge of the atom in question.

In many cases, the absolute values of the Gibbs energies of ions are determined by coupling the conventional values of ions with respect to H₂(g) with absolute values of H⁺ ion using eqs. (2) and (3).

The absolute value of $\Delta H^0_{\text{h}}(\text{H}^+)$ was determined by Halliwell and Nyburg⁷⁴ using eqs. (2) and (3).

We have

$$[\Delta H^0_{\text{conv}}(\text{M}^+) - \Delta H^0_{\text{conv}}(\text{X}^-)] = [\Delta H^0_{\text{abs}}(\text{M}^+) - \Delta H^0_{\text{abs}}(\text{X}^-)] - 2\Delta H^0_{\text{abs}}(\text{H}^+)_{\text{h}} \quad (46)$$

Following Buchingham⁶⁶, Halliwell and Nyburg⁷⁴, the eq. (46) becomes eq. (47) for ions of equal radii.

$$[\Delta H^0_{\text{conv}}(\text{M}^+) - \Delta H^0_{\text{conv}}(\text{X}^-)] = -2\Delta H^0_{\text{h,abs}}(\text{H}^+) + 4NZ_i e p_w / (r_i + r_s)^3 \quad (47)$$

as Born, ion-dipole and ion-induced dipole terms for positive and negative ions with equal r -values cancel.

Thus the plot of LHS against $1/(r_i + r_s)^3$ extrapolated to infinite radius (i.e. $1/(r_i + r_s) \rightarrow 0$) gives $\Delta H^0_{\text{abs}}(\text{H}^+)_{\text{h or s}}$. However, the method is defective as :

- (i) Cations and anions of equal radii are not usually available.
- (ii) Formation of cations and anions are endothermic and exothermic respectively contrary to Born equation. Even in case of Born charging, energies for cations and anions with equal r_i -values should be different due to different effective charge of the central ion.
- (iii) Ion-dipole and ion-quadrupole values for cations and anions are not equal but rather opposite in sign so cancellation of these terms is not possible.
- (iv) $\Delta G_{\text{conv}}^0(X^-)$ values utilized in the calculation are secondary values as they are obtained by subtracting $\Delta G^0(M^+)$ from $\Delta G_{\text{soln}}^0(MX)$ which are mainly dependent on the lattice energies of the different electrolytes and validity of the ionic additivity principle.

Naturally the values are defective.

In recent years, Tissandier *et al.*³² and Kelly *et al.*³⁴ determined absolute enthalpy and Gibbs energy of solvation of ions in aqueous and some organic solvents from cluster ion solvation data utilizing the principle of additivity of ions. These values are presented in Tables A and B. They consider the values to be most accurate.

Table A. Absolute values of Gibbs energy of solvation (kJ mol^{-1}) in water and other organic solvents determined by Kelly *et al.*

Ions	Water	CH ₃ OH	CH ₃ CN	DMSO
Na ⁺	-431.8	-423.0	-423.0	-455.6
K ⁺	-359.8	-348.5	-357.7	-385.8
Rb ⁺	-337.2	-299.2	-342.2	-
Cs ⁺	-314.2	-	-302.9	-
Cl ⁻	-311.7	-299.2	-261.1	-262.3
Br ⁻	-285.8	-275.3	-248.1	-250.2
I ⁻	-250.6	-243.5	-221.8	-

Table B. Absolute values of enthalpy and Gibbs energy of solvation (kJ mol^{-1}) in water determined by Tissandier *et al.*

Ions	$\Delta G_{\text{h}}^0(\text{i})$	$\Delta H_{\text{h}}^0(\text{i})$	$\Delta H_{\text{aq}}^0(\text{i})$
H ⁺	-1104.5	-1150.1	-1152.6
Li ⁺	-529.4	-578.9	-576.1
Na ⁺	-423.8	-463.5	-466.5
K ⁺	-352.0	-380.2	-381.3
Rb ⁺	-329.3	-355.6	-357.0
F ⁻	-428.8	-463.9	-456.9
Cl ⁻	-304.2	-319.9	-316.3
Br ⁻	-277.4	-288.9	-282.7
I ⁻	-240.0	-247.7	-245.9

The results reported by most of the workers did not consider ion-solvent interactions. However, ion-solvent interactions are universal phenomenon and should be considered though the nature of the interactions in solution are not fully understood.

The thermodynamic values for the hydration or solvation of ions and the related values in aqueous and organic solutions without interactions and with interactions are presented in Tables 3–16. Single ion values determined by us can be considered to be reliable as the main contributing factor is the energy involved in charging an atom into ion. The most authentic and reliable values are IP or EA. The contributions from other terms are small. The accuracy of the single ion values cannot be predicted properly but the accuracy of the values may be taken to be within $\pm(5-10) \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

Our values for cations are more negative than those presented by other workers. The consideration of the interaction terms makes the values more negative though the values for the anions are positive.

The recent values of Tissandier *et al.*³², Kelly *et al.*³⁴, are based on cluster-ion solvation data. Ions at low concentration are allowed to react with large excess of gaseous solvent molecules at high pressure in the reaction chamber. The solvent pressure is kept sufficiently high ($\approx 5-15$ Torr) so that the ions are permitted sufficient time to allow the attainment of equilibrium between the various clustering sequences. The primary ions and the ion-clusters leak through a small orifice into high-vacuum where they were mass analysed and counted. The data were analysed to calculate equilibrium constants etc.

The ions are converted to ion-H₂O clusters. As hydration increases, cluster-ion size increases and becomes maximum with $n = 6$, and no further solvation occurs and the energy changes in the formation $M^{\pm}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n$ is taken to be equivalent to solvation energy of ions. Tissandier *et al.*³² considered the differences in properties of a pair of oppositely charged cluster ions in terms of their conventional solvation properties. As the cluster ions get large, the ionic subcomponents become essentially fully solvated, leaving nothing to be accomplished by further solvation and no further differences between different ions. According to Klots⁷⁵,

Table 14. THF

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -565.41 (122.09)	(i) -562.61 (84.39)	(i) -447.22 (240.28)	(i) -444.27 (202.73)	(i) -0.01 (0.13)
	(ii) -550.78 (136.72)	(ii) -549.39 (97.61)	(ii) -444.29 (243.21)	(ii) -442.91 (204.09)	(ii) -0.01 (0.13)
Na ⁺	(i) -512.27 (97.73)	(i) -552.48 (20.32)	(i) -422.29 (187.71)	(i) -462.52 (110.28)	(i) 0.14 (0.26)
	(ii) -498.21 (111.79)	(ii) -539.89 (32.91)	(ii) -418.59 (191.41)	(ii) -460.27 (112.53)	(ii) 0.14 (0.26)
K ⁺	(i) -417.15 (97.95)	(i) -418.85 (60.55)	(i) -348.09 (167.01)	(i) -349.79 (129.61)	(i) 0.01 (0.13)
	(ii) -403.51 (111.59)	(ii) -407.20 (72.20)	(ii) -341.99 (173.11)	(ii) -345.68 (133.72)	(ii) 0.01 (0.13)
Rb ⁺	(i) -393.16 (98.04)	(i) -396.22 (59.98)	(i) -330.46 (160.74)	(i) -333.53 (122.67)	(i) 0.01 (0.13)
	(ii) -378.57 (112.63)	(ii) -384.04 (72.16)	(ii) -322.44 (168.76)	(ii) -327.92 (128.28)	(ii) 0.02 (0.14)
Cs ⁺	(i) -353.86 (106.04)	(i) -359.28 (66.02)	(i) -298.73 (161.17)	(i) -304.15 (121.15)	(i) 0.02 (0.13)
	(ii) -343.83 (116.07)	(ii) -351.02 (74.28)	(ii) -292.44 (167.46)	(ii) -299.63 (125.67)	(ii) 0.02 (0.14)
F ⁻	(i) 369.49 (114.39)	(i) 360.72 (95.02)	(i) 306.32 (51.22)	(i) 297.55 (31.85)	(i) 0.03 (0.07)
	(ii) 375.69 (120.59)	(ii) 367.45 (101.75)	(ii) 305.26 (50.16)	(ii) 297.01 (31.31)	(ii) 0.03 (0.06)
Cl ⁻	(i) 371.75 (137.75)	(i) 361.70 (118.30)	(i) 323.29 (89.29)	(i) 313.24 (69.84)	(i) 0.03 (0.07)
	(ii) 374.68 (140.68)	(ii) 365.09 (121.69)	(ii) 322.22 (88.22)	(ii) 312.63 (69.23)	(ii) 0.03 (0.06)
Br ⁻	(i) 349.13 (130.33)	(i) 338.26 (96.06)	(i) 304.24 (85.44)	(i) 293.36 (51.16)	(i) 0.04 (0.12)
	(ii) 351.28 (132.48)	(ii) 340.87 (98.67)	(ii) 303.09 (84.29)	(ii) 292.67 (50.47)	(ii) 0.04 (0.11)
I ⁻	(i) 321.11 (126.61)	(i) 309.25 (84.25)	(i) 280.89 (86.39)	(i) 269.04 (44.04)	(i) 0.04 (0.14)
	(ii) 321.92 (127.42)	(ii) 310.70 (85.70)	(ii) 279.56 (85.06)	(ii) 268.35 (43.35)	(ii) 0.04 (0.14)

Table 15. 1,4-Dioxan

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -503.62 (183.88)	(i) -502.62 (144.38)	(i) -278.59 (408.91)	(i) -277.59 (369.41)	(i) 0.00 (0.13)
	(ii) -473.84 (213.66)	(ii) -474.22 (172.78)	(ii) -275.88 (411.62)	(ii) -276.26 (370.74)	(ii) 0.00 (0.14)
Na ⁺	(i) -423.12 (186.88)	(i) -423.39 (149.41)	(i) -261.82 (348.18)	(i) -262.09 (310.71)	(i) 0.00 (0.13)
	(ii) -393.99 (216.01)	(ii) -398.84 (173.96)	(ii) -258.02 (351.98)	(ii) 259.87 (312.93)	(ii) 0.01 (0.14)
K ⁺	(i) -329.15 (185.95)	(i) -332.34 (147.06)	(i) -212.39 (302.71)	(i) -215.59 (263.81)	(i) 0.01 (0.13)
	(ii) -307.92 (207.18)	(ii) -312.61 (166.79)	(ii) -206.55 (308.55)	(ii) -211.51 (267.89)	(ii) 0.02 (0.14)
Rb ⁺	(i) -303.92 (187.28)	(i) -308.22 (147.98)	(i) -200.19 (291.01)	(i) -204.48 (251.72)	(i) 0.01 (0.13)
	(ii) -282.91 (208.29)	(ii) -289.48 (166.72)	(ii) -192.35 (298.85)	(ii) -198.92 (257.28)	(ii) 0.02 (0.14)
Cs ⁺	(i) -266.02 (193.88)	(i) -272.56 (152.74)	(i) -177.43 (282.47)	(i) -183.97 (241.33)	(i) 0.02 (0.14)
	(ii) -252.64 (207.26)	(ii) -260.74 (164.56)	(ii) -171.39 (288.51)	(ii) -179.49 (245.81)	(ii) 0.03 (0.14)
F ⁻	(i) 261.42 (6.32)	(i) 254.83 (-10.87)	(i) 197.17 (-57.93)	(i) 190.58 (-75.12)	(i) 0.02 (0.06)
	(ii) 267.79 (12.69)	(ii) 261.69 (-4.01)	(ii) 196.15 (-58.95)	(ii) 190.05 (-75.65)	(ii) 0.02 (0.06)
Cl ⁻	(i) 258.01 (24.01)	(i) 250.42 (7.02)	(i) 209.03 (-24.97)	(i) 201.44 (-41.96)	(i) 0.03 (0.06)
	(ii) 261.10 (27.10)	(ii) 253.99 (10.59)	(ii) 207.94 (-26.06)	(ii) 200.84 (-42.56)	(ii) 0.02 (0.06)
Br ⁻	(i) 242.91 (24.11)	(i) 234.48 (-7.72)	(i) 197.68 (-21.12)	(i) 189.25 (-52.95)	(i) 0.03 (0.11)
	(ii) 246.86 (28.06)	(ii) 238.88 (-3.32)	(ii) 196.55 (-22.25)	(ii) 188.57 (-53.63)	(ii) 0.03 (0.11)
I ⁻	(i) 223.76 (29.26)	(i) 214.51 (-10.49)	(i) 183.47 (-11.03)	(i) 174.22 (-50.78)	(i) 0.03 (0.13)
	(ii) 222.97 (28.47)	(ii) 216.08 (-8.92)	(ii) 180.43 (-14.07)	(ii) 173.54 (-51.46)	(ii) 0.02 (0.13)

$$L_{t_{n \rightarrow \alpha}} \{ \Delta H_{aq}^0 [B^-(H_2O)_n(g)] - \Delta H_{aq}^0 [A^+(H_2O)_n(g)] \} = 0 \quad (48)$$

In general, n is supposed to be six for ions. The value of $\Delta H_{aq}^0(H^+)$ or $\Delta G_{aq}^0(H^+)$ is obtained from the plot of

$\Delta H_{aq}^0(H^+)$ (approx) (kJ/mol) or $\Delta G_{aq}^0(H^+)$ (approx) (kJ/mol) against $[\Delta H_n^0(A^+) - \Delta H_n^0(B^-)]$ (kJ mol⁻¹) or $[\Delta G_n^0(A^+) - \Delta G_n^0(B^-)]$ (kJ mol⁻¹) i.e. cluster pair based $\Delta H_{aq}^0(H^+)$ or $\Delta G_{aq}^0(H^+)$ vs the difference in cluster-ion

Table 16. Acetonitrile

I	II	III	IV	V	VI
Li ⁺	(i) -610.65 (76.85)	(i) -606.49 (40.51)	(i) -501.57 (185.93)	(i) -497.42 (149.58)	(i) -0.01 (0.12)
	(ii) -597.57 (89.93)	(ii) -595.00 (52.00)	(ii) -498.57 (188.93)	(ii) -496.00 (151.00)	(ii) -0.01 (0.13)
Na ⁺	(i) -558.99 (51.01)	(i) -556.80 (16.00)	(i) -473.80 (136.20)	(i) -471.62 (101.18)	(i) -0.00 (0.12)
	(ii) -545.99 (64.01)	(ii) -545.88 (26.92)	(ii) -469.39 (140.61)	(ii) -469.27 (103.53)	(ii) 0.00 (0.12)
K ⁺	(i) -458.17 (56.93)	(i) -460.01 (19.39)	(i) -390.32 (124.78)	(i) -392.15 (87.25)	(i) 0.01 (0.13)
	(ii) -444.59 (70.51)	(ii) -449.45 (29.95)	(ii) -382.99 (132.11)	(ii) -387.85 (91.55)	(ii) 0.02 (0.14)
Rb ⁺	(i) -433.04 (58.16)	(i) -436.69 (19.51)	(i) -370.46 (120.74)	(i) -374.11 (82.09)	(i) 0.01 (0.13)
	(ii) -417.83 (73.37)	(ii) -425.32 (30.88)	(ii) -360.75 (130.45)	(ii) -368.23 (87.97)	(ii) 0.03 (0.14)
Cs ⁺	(i) -390.45 (69.45)	(i) -397.86 (27.44)	(i) -334.19 (125.71)	(i) -341.61 (83.69)	(i) 0.03 (0.14)
	(ii) -379.73 (80.17)	(ii) -389.96 (35.34)	(ii) -326.64 (133.26)	(ii) -336.87 (88.43)	(ii) 0.03 (0.15)
F ⁻	(i) 367.68 (112.58)	(i) 358.82 (93.12)	(i) 342.10 (87.00)	(i) 333.24 (67.54)	(i) 0.03 (0.07)
	(ii) 364.17 (109.07)	(ii) 355.92 (90.22)	(ii) 340.94 (85.84)	(ii) 332.68 (66.98)	(ii) 0.03 (0.06)
Cl ⁻	(i) 389.16 (155.16)	(i) 378.30 (134.90)	(i) 361.43 (127.43)	(i) 350.57 (107.17)	(i) 0.04 (0.07)
	(ii) 387.69 (153.69)	(ii) 377.44 (134.04)	(ii) 360.19 (126.19)	(ii) 349.94 (106.54)	(ii) 0.03 (0.07)
Br ⁻	(i) 367.84 (149.04)	(i) 355.94 (113.74)	(i) 340.15 (121.35)	(i) 328.25 (86.05)	(i) 0.04 (0.12)
	(ii) 366.54 (147.74)	(ii) 355.27 (113.07)	(ii) 338.80 (120.00)	(ii) 327.53 (85.33)	(ii) 0.04 (0.12)
I ⁻	(i) 341.21 (146.71)	(i) 328.26 (103.26)	(i) 313.90 (119.40)	(i) 300.96 (75.96)	(i) 0.04 (0.15)
	(ii) 340.09 (145.59)	(ii) 327.77 (102.77)	(ii) 312.55 (118.05)	(ii) 300.24 (75.24)	(ii) 0.04 (0.14)

solvation enthalpy or Gibbs energy for various cluster sizes. The $\Delta H_{\text{aq}}^0(\text{H}^+)$ or $\Delta G_{\text{aq}}^0(\text{H}^+)$ approximation is good at only one particular pair of ions, so each data set at a particular cluster size share a common point³². The values are utilized to calculate the solvation energy of other ions.

However, there is a conceptual differences in the method of determining $\Delta H_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{H}^+)_{\text{h or s}}$ and $\Delta G_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{H}^+)_{\text{h or s}}$ and other ions using cluster-ion solvation data and those determined in the present work and in the literature. In the former method ions are converted into ion-H₂O clusters. As hydration increases, cluster size increases and becomes maximum with $n = 6$ (not in every case). No further solvation or hydration has been assumed and energy changes involved are equated to $\Delta H_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{M}^+)_{\text{h or s}}$ $\Delta H_{\text{abs}}^0(\text{X}^-)_{\text{h or s}}$ etc.

The calculations are based on the cycle represented in Fig. 3.

Obviously, the energetics of reaction (hydration) in the gaseous state is completely different from those in solution. In the hydration process (Fig. 1), M⁺ or X⁻ is not hydrated in the gaseous state, the ions are hydrated only when the ion goes into bulk solvent of relative permittivity ϵ unlike the reaction suggested by Tissandier *et al.*, Kelly *et al.* (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3

The hydration is :

In solution, ion undergoes a number of interactions (not fully realized) and there are rearrangements of the solvent molecules.

In the gaseous state few molecules of ion and excess solvent (H₂O) molecules (still the numbers are small) are involved at high pressure and temperature. Analysis of data are also made under different conditions and extrapolated values are taken. The reactions are microscopic in nature and are dependent on the particular ion and few solvent molecules (not solvent molecules in a bulk), and the result is not related to solvent properties. But M⁺_{aq} and X⁻_{aq} determined are dependent on the macroscopic properties of solvents like relative permittivity, polarisabilities,

refractive index, surface tension etc. and other factors and the solvated molecules belong to entire phase⁷⁶⁻⁷⁸. Moreover, there are different interactions of M^+ or X^- with solvent molecules. The orientations of solvent molecules around the ions and the solvation numbers of cations and anions in water and other solvents are known to be different^{21,67}. Thus, the hydration energies of the ions in bulk solvent are likely to be different from those in the gas phase and the values given by Tissandier *et al.* should also be different.

The main contributory factor for hydration or solvation of ions is deionization ($-IP$ or $-EA$). Contributions from II and III (solvation of gaseous H or M or X atom and charging to H^+ or M^+ or X^- ion in solvents) will be small and positive. Thus, $\Delta G^0(M^+ \text{ or } X^-)_{\text{hydration}}$ should be close to $-IP$ or $-EA$ (numerically a little less). The values reported by Tissandier *et al.* for $\Delta H^0(H^+)_{\text{h}}$ and $\Delta G^0(H^+)_{\text{h}}$ and other ions are much higher. But if interaction terms are considered, the value of $\Delta H^0(H^+)$ and $\Delta G^0(H^+)$ should be more negative for cations and less positive for anions and the ions will be stabilized in aqueous and other solvents.

In solution, the ions will be stabilized by enthalpy and Gibbs energy of formation in solution as in the gaseous state and solid state. However, study of the nature of ion-solvation and ion-solvent interactions should be pursued to expose the role of solvents in thermodynamics, kinetics and transport properties of electrolytes in solution.

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